

The Fuzzy Median and the Fuzzy MAD

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Abstract*

An extension of two key robust statistics to fuzzy sets is presented and applied to the fuzzy c-means clustering algorithm. Examples of a robust statistic are the median and the median absolute deviation from the median or MAD, a robust estimate of dispersion. These extensions are derived, and the fuzzy median is applied to the fuzzy c-means clustering algorithm. The modified clustering algorithm shows improved performance in clustering data sets generated by heavy-tailed distributions like the Cauchy distribution.

1: Introduction

One goal of robust statistics is to design statistics that are more resistant to outliers. Two examples of these statistics are the median for estimating the center of the data and the median absolute deviation from the median (MAD) for estimating the dispersion of the data. However, these statistics have *not* been designed to work with fuzzy sets. Both statistics are based on order statistics that do not inherently take into account the possible membership of data points in more than one set. This paper first discusses a fuzzy median and a fuzzy MAD estimator. When these estimators are used in conjunction with the fuzzy c-means algorithm, the result is a more robust algorithm. The modified algorithm is shown to improve clustering on data sets generated by a heavy-tailed distribution.

2: Fuzzy Robust Statistics

Robust statistics is an area of study that deals with variations from the ideal assumptions [1-5], including the design of statistics that are resistant to outliers. These statistics are sometimes evaluated by the percentage of outliers that must be present before the

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statistic no longer gives a meaningful estimate of the desired quantity. The first example of this is the median, which can take almost 50% outliers before it loses its ability to measure the center of the data. The second is the MAD estimate, which measures the dispersion of the data sample. It too has a high breakdown point. In this section, the median and the MAD are defined and the source of their resistant behavior is explained. Then, alternative definitions are given that can be generalized to apply to fuzzy data sets. *Throughout this section, the data samples are assumed to be one dimensional. When these statistics are applied to higher dimensional samples, it is on a component-by-component basis.*

Suppose the data set is $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$, where each element x_i , is a p -dimensional vector. If $p = 1$, so that the samples are real numbers, then the median of X is defined in terms of the order statistics. The ordered N -sample is $\{x_{(1)}, x_{(2)}, \dots, x_{(N)}\}$ where by definition $x_{(1)} \leq x_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq x_{(N)}$ and the parenthesized subscript indicates that the original data has been re-labeled or permuted so now the sample set is ordered. Then, the median of X is defined to be $x_{(l+1)}$ if $N = 2l + 1$, and $[x_{(l)} + x_{(l+1)}] / 2$ if $N = 2l$. If $p > 1$, then the definition is applied to each dimension of the sample and the median vector is constructed from the vector of individual medians. Since the median is defined in terms of the ordered sample, it is an order statistic and there appears to be no way to extend it to a fuzzy set. In one dimension, the median represents the half-way point of the samples, having an equal number of samples smaller and larger than itself. This interpretation explains why almost half of the data points must be outliers before the median loses its effectiveness as a measure of centrality. Half of the points to the left say, must be outliers, before the median is pulled off to the left. In fact, the finite breakdown point of the median is one-half [1].

The robust estimator of dispersion called the MAD, is also an order statistic. This statistic is defined as the median of the absolute deviations from the median. To construct this statistic, take the samples $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ and construct another data set

$Y = \{|x_1 - med(X)|, |x_2 - med(X)|, \dots, |x_N - med(X)|\}$, find the median of this set and then scale it. For this paper, the MAD is defined as $mad(X) = med(Y) / 0.6745$, where the constant 0.6745 adjusts the dispersion measure to be 1 when the sample is Gaussian with unit variance. Intuitively, one folds the data about the $med(X)$ and then finds the median of the set of positive deviations from the median. The breakdown point of the MAD is also one-half [1, p. 107].

Although the median and the MAD are resistant to outliers, they are constructed on crisp sets, i.e., the set of data points X and the set of absolute deviations from the median Y , are crisp sets. Inherently, order statistics do not take account of the degree of membership of each point in the data set. However, if these statistics are reformulated, then the membership of the samples in the sets can be taken into account. This is accomplished by using another definition of the median, which does not depend upon the linear ordering of the samples. The median can be defined as the solution m of [5, p. 233]

$$\min_{m \in R} \sum_{k=1}^N |x_k - m|.$$

This can be seen most easily by taking the derivative with respect to m , so one wants

$$\sum_{k=1}^N sgn(x_k - m) = 0.$$

If $N = 2l + 1$, this occurs at the point $m = x_{(l+1)}$ and for $N = 2l$ the derivative is zero for any $m \in (x_{(l)}, x_{(l+1)})$.

The root m is not unique, but it can easily be made unique by choosing a suitable point within this interval, e.g., the average of $x_{(l+1)}$ and $x_{(l)}$. This definition is amenable to generalization to fuzzy sets. For the c class problem, if u_{ik} is the membership of x_k in class i , then m_i solves

$$\min_{m_i \in R} \sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik} |x_k - m_i|$$

and the statistic m_i has the characteristics of a median and applies to the fuzzy set $X_i = u_{i1}/x_1 +$

$u_{i2}/x_2 + \dots + u_{iN}/x_N$. $\{m_i\}_{i=1}^c$ is precisely the set that is used to update the exemplars in modified fuzzy c -means. The derivative also exists and is given by

$$\sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik} sgn(x_k - m_i) = 0.$$

Numerically solving for the root of this functional using bisection yields both the root and the fuzzy median estimate of the set.

The limiting cases of this statistic are consistent. If $u_{ik} = u_i(x_k) = 1, \forall k$, then the definition reverts to the

standard median. For the two class problem, if $N = 2l$ and the first $N/2$ samples are from class 1 and the second $N/2$ are from class 2, then

$$u_{1k} = u_1(x_k) = \begin{cases} 1, & k \leq N/2 \\ 0, & k > N/2 \end{cases} \text{ and}$$

$$u_{2k} = u_2(x_k) = \begin{cases} 0, & k \leq N/2 \\ 1, & k > N/2 \end{cases}.$$

The resulting fuzzy medians reduce to the crisp medians of both of the crisp subsets associated with the classes. The fuzzy median is a measure of central tendency that also reflects the membership of the sample points in the fuzzy set and reduces to the crisp median where appropriate.

The MAD estimate can also be reformulated in the functional form

$$\min_{\eta \in R} \sum_{k=1}^N |x_k - m| - \eta$$

and the resulting MAD estimate is $mad = \eta / 0.6745$. Note that this requires that the median m be known beforehand. For a fuzzy data set, the median does not exist; however, the fuzzy median does. So one can define the fuzzy MAD recursively for the i -th fuzzy data set by assuming the fuzzy median m_i exists. The functional form is now defined by

$$\min_{\eta_i \in R} \sum_{k=1}^N |x_k - m_i| - \eta_i$$

and the fuzzy MAD is given by $fuzmad_i = \eta_i / 0.6745$.

From an implementation point of view, one first forms the fuzzy median m_i , uses this to construct a new fuzzy data set $Y_i = u_{i1}/|x_1 - m_i| + u_{i2}/|x_2 - m_i| + \dots + u_{iN}/|x_N - m_i|$, finds the fuzzy median on this set, and then scales it. To apply these statistics on a p -dimensional space, one has to apply them on each component separately.

Although this approach involves a simple modification of these statistics, it allows the important application of robust statistics to fuzzy sets. The median is an M-estimator or Huber's generalization of the maximum likelihood estimator. Many times these estimators m are formulated implicitly by specifying functionals of the form

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \rho(x_k - m),$$

where ρ satisfies certain boundary, symmetry, and non-negativity conditions. It would seem that all these functionals could be weighted with the appropriate membership functions, thus allowing this whole class of estimators to be applied to fuzzy algorithm development.

3: Robust Fuzzy c-Means

At each iteration, the fuzzy c-means algorithm depends on one or two estimates made upon the fuzzy subsets associated with the c classes [6-9]. First, a linear combination of data points is used to estimate the exemplars of the fuzzy classes. Second, the new membership values are estimated based upon the distance to the exemplars, which may or may not be normed with the inverse of the fuzzy covariance matrix of the data sets. In the robust fuzzy c-means, linear statistics are replaced with the corresponding fuzzy robust statistics. Thus for each class, the sample mean is replaced with the fuzzy median. The class covariance matrix may be replaced by a diagonal approximation $\Sigma_i = \text{diag}(\text{fuzmad}_i^2(X), \dots, \text{fuzmad}_i^2(X))$, based upon the fuzzy MAD to construct the Mahalanobis norms [9]. In the following examples, the exemplars are calculated using the fuzzy median, but the covariance matrix is taken to be the identity matrix.

Figure 1 shows the exemplar tracks for two antipodal Gaussian clusters with identity covariance matrices. The data is five dimensional simulated data. Figure 1a shows the trace of the fuzzy c-means algorithm (without covariance estimation) with initial starting points at $(0, \pm 1, 0, 0, 0)$. Figure 1b shows the corresponding plot for the robust fuzzy c-means. The asterisk symbol "*" and "o" denote the two cluster centers through 20 iterations. The population means for the two clusters are at antipodal positions of $(\pm 1.27, 0, 0, 0, 0)$. The algorithms appear to converge to different centers because the sample mean and the sample median are different from each other. This figure represents only one set of exemplar trajectories. Further study of the convergence rates and trajectories is continuing with fuzzy covariance matrices used to norm the distances.

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1. Comparison of fuzzy c-means and robust fuzzy c-means exemplar tracks for two Gaussian clusters with centers at $(\pm 1.27, 0, 0, 0, 0)$.

Figure 2 shows a similar exemplar trajectory superimposed on the two dimensional Cauchy clusters produced by the robust fuzzy c-means. The corresponding trajectories for fuzzy c-means do not converge to the cluster centers in the twenty steps. The divergence is caused by a few large magnitude outliers destroying the weighted mean used in the fuzzy c-means algorithm and the number of clusters being fixed at two. Note because of the scale used in figure 2, the outliers caused by the heavy-tailed distributions do not appear in the figure. The robust fuzzy c-means has the same susceptibility to local stagnation as the fuzzy c-means.

Figure 2. Robust fuzzy c-means convergence on two Cauchy clusters located at antipodal positions. Because of the scale used in the figure, the points shown do not include the outliers.

4: Conclusions

Two fuzzy order statistics were developed, the fuzzy median and the fuzzy MAD. Order statistics are defined on crisp sets. Before these statistics can be applied to fuzzy data sets, they must be generalized to take into account the membership of the data points in the fuzzy sets. This was done by properly weighting the functionals that generate the statistics with the membership values of the data points. In fuzzy algorithms, the fuzzy median can replace the weighted average and the fuzzy MAD can replace the standard deviation. The fuzzy median was applied within the fuzzy c-means clustering algorithm and an example was shown where this stabilized the convergence when the number of clusters was fixed and the data was heavy-tailed. The fuzzy MAD can also be used to generate an approximate covariance matrix replacement. The general approach used to fuzzify robust statistics is currently being applied to more sophisticated robust estimates of location and scale and the results will be reported when available. The replacement of linear estimates by more resistant fuzzy estimators in any fuzzy algorithm should make the algorithm more robust.

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